

Ultrawide Band Sensor Design for Early Breast Cancer Detection

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Abstract— Cancer is still a major worldwide health concern, thus developing new, efficient, low-power, and highly accurate early detection methods is imperative. Ultra-wideband (UWB) technology offers a viable way to improve the efficiency and accuracy of cancer diagnosis. This study offers a thorough analysis of the creation and design of sensors for early detection. This research has also examined the interaction between the developed antenna and breast models with tumorlike features. Simulations have been run to assess several parameters, including return loss, voltage standing wave ratio (VSWR), directivity, gains, and radiation patterns. The findings showed that the antenna array had high impedance matching, efficient energy transmission, a bandwidth of 2.3 GHz to 12.35 GHz, resonance at 5.4 GHz, and the ability to identify tumours with accuracy. Three antennas and five antenna configurations have been examined to assess the antenna's accuracy in detecting breast tumours. Antennas were strategically positioned on breast models to optimise sensitivity. The outcomes of various configurations show that the array can precisely identify signals linked to tumours, suggesting the possibility of early breast cancer detection.)

Keywords— Sensor, ultra-wideband; breast cancer, tumour detection, return loss, radiation pattern, antenna Configuration.

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the most common cancers that affects women worldwide is breast cancer (BC). In 2020, 685,000 lives were lost due to its consequences, affecting 2.3 million women. By the end of 2020, BC had become the most common disease worldwide, with 7.8 million women having received a diagnosis in the five years prior. Globally, it results in more women losing disability-adjusted life years (DALYs) from it than from any other type of cancer. After puberty, BC can appear in women of any age, with incidence rates often rising with advancing years. Remarkably, BC death rates remained unchanged between the 1930s and the 1970s. However, advancements in Commencing from the 1980s, countries that

introduced early detection strategies witnessed the initiation of improved survival rates. and various therapeutic interventions to combat invasive forms of the disease [1].

The need for an accurate, affordable, and tiny UWB-based sensor for breast cancer detection (BCD) has increased. This study was motivated by the urgent need to address breast cancer, a significant global public health concern. The potential use of ultra-wideband (UWB) technology in the early diagnosis of breast cancer has been studied. With a frequency range of 3.1 GHz to 10.6 GHz, the UWB spectrum is extremely promising for use in a variety of technological fields, including Internet of Things (IoT), wireless networks, wireless power transfer and electromagnetic energy harvesting [2]-[4]. Recognizing its versatility, the US Federal Communication Commission acknowledged the numerous possibilities of UWB technology in 2002 [5]. Considering the state of breast cancer diagnostic techniques today, limitations in early detection and diagnostic accuracy seem like compelling situations. In recent times, there has been an increased focus on alternative imaging and sensing techniques to improve breast cancer diagnoses (BCDs). In the field of technological breakthroughs, Ultra-wideband (UWB) technology has become a major contender because of its unique features and potential applications in medical diagnostics. The short duration and wide frequency range of UWB signals allow them to pass through biological tissues with little attenuation [6].

Early detection and accurate diagnosis are necessary to enhance treatment outcomes and death rates for BC. Although mammography and ultrasound are two popular traditional methods for BC screening, they have limitations regarding patient comfort, sensitivity, and specificity. Microwave imaging is a precise and promising approach that offers low cost and safety benefits.

The work by [7] developed a cost-effective UWB patch antenna on an FR4 substrate. This antenna offers a peak gain of 6.43 dBi and a wide bandwidth enabling high-resolution imaging and deep tissue penetration, crucial for tumor identification. Its UWB range (3.22 to 11.92 GHz) suits Breast Cancer Detection (BCD) due to minimal tissue attenuation. A micro-strip patch antenna operating at MV frequencies for early-stage breast cancer identification. The work done in [8] has designed an innovative UWB antenna that uses a polyimide PI as the substrate. The antenna effectively covers the full range of UWB band 1.60 to 16.40 GHz, with measured and simulated impedance bandwidths. It achieves acceptable omnidirectional radiation patterns at frequencies of 2.45 to 5.2 GHz with an overall maximum realized gain exceeding 2.8 dB in the UWB band.

The design and optimisation of UWB sensors require sophisticated computational techniques in addition to an understanding of the electromagnetic properties of breast tissue [9]. CST software, a well-known electromagnetic simulation tool, offers a solid foundation for designing and analysing complex sensor systems. CST software can be used to accurately model electromagnetic wave propagation, antenna characteristics, and sensor performance [10]. Research may include various sensor configurations, optimization of design parameters, and assessing the efficacy of UWB sensors for BCD by using CST software tools.

II. ANTENNA CHARACTERIZATION

Early on in our research, we conducted a thorough investigation of several sensor designs for BCD and other possible applications, especially in relation to Ultra-Wideband (UWB) technology. We examined the radiation parameters of the antenna design, verified its performance, and optimised the sensor for precise and early BCD using CST Microwave Studio simulations. The antenna's bandwidth can be increased with a proven method that involves inserting a rectangular component behind the circular patch. This is important for UWB applications. The feedline architecture of our sensor was selected using coplanar waveguide technology to guarantee effective signal transmission and reduce signal losses.

Using Coplanar Waveguide technology [11], the proposed circular microstrip patch antenna has a balanced feed, lower feed line radiation, and is appropriate for ultra-wideband applications. It is made for usage at ultra-wideband frequencies. The selected substrate is made of polyimide lossy material, which has a thickness of 0.0027 mm and a modest dielectric constant of ($\epsilon_r = 3.5$). The patch, microstrip line, and ground plane are all composed of copper to reduce signal losses and guarantee proper impedance matching. To improve bandwidth and impedance matching, the antenna design, shown in Figure 1, consists of a circular patch with a rectangle extension behind it. The antenna's gain, bandwidth, and S11 characteristics are further enhanced by the creation

of two ground sections using the coplanar waveguide approach. The rectangular patch is placed behind the substrate; Table 1 provides the exact measurements. These parameters are used after a few changes and simulation results to make a perfect UWB antenna.

Table 1: Final Parameters of the antenna

Parameter	Dimension(mm)
Ls	50.50
Ws	37
Ts	0.8
Tg	0.85
Wg	16.50
Lg	10.80
Lf	11.50
Wf	2.50
Rp	18
Wp	5.65
Lp	1

(a) Top View of the Design Antenna

(b) Bottom View of the Design Antenna

Figure 1: Structure of the Proposed Antenna Design

III. BREAST PHANTOM EVALUATION

This study uses a complex breast model that is simulated in CST software to explore the complex relationship between electromagnetic waves and real breast tissue. The model is a half-sphere with an outside radius of 25 mm and a skin layer that represents the structure of a human breast in simplified form. Layers of fat and fibro glandular breast tissue are nested within; these have distinct conductivities and dielectric constants. Significantly, a faulty cell is injected into the fibro glandular tissue, providing a focus for examination. The study focuses on discrepancies in outcomes, especially about exposure to electromagnetic waves. The goal of the inquiry is to understand the subtle behaviours of the breast model under various settings by adopting features corresponding to 5.4 GHz. It is recognised that individual differences in age, hormones, genetics, and ethnicity can affect the dielectric characteristics of breast tissue. Therefore, even though this study provides insightful information, more research is necessary to examine the various ways in which these factors affect the results. Table 2 shows different layers properties of Breast model.

Figure 2: Antenna with Breast model

Figure 3: A small tumour tested in a breast model

Table 2: Breast phantom design using CST having different layers Properties

Dielectric Medium	Permittivity (F/m)	Conductivity(S/m)
Skin	35.4	3.45
Fat	9.94	0.77
Fibro_Grandular Tissue	52.71	5.15
Tumor	18	1.05

IV. ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

A. Antenna performance and analysis

To determine the antenna's performance, CST software was used to simulate it first. To determine the antenna's return loss and improve performance, it was simulated using CST software, as Figure 4 subsequently demonstrated. According to the simulation results, the antenna ranges from 2.38 to 12.35 GHz with a bandwidth of 10 GHz. The antenna has a high resonance frequency of 5.4 GHz. As seen in Figure 5, the far field radiation pattern reveals that the antenna's gain is roughly 3.42 dBi. These results show that the antenna has robust impedance properties and performs well for transmitting signals within the given range.

Figure 4: Simulated return loss of the proposed Antenna

Figure 5: Gain of the Proposed Design Antenna

B. Results of the Breast Model research with and without a tumour

The antenna's S-parameters have changed, as indicated by the simulation results displayed in Figures 6 and 7. When comparing the S-parameter simulated with the phantom containing the tumour to the simulation without the tumour, a deeper response is observed, which suggests that the antenna impedance matching or scattering behaviour has changed. This illustrates a drop in antenna radiation intensity in the direction of the main lobe. The main lobe in the far-field gain at 5.4 GHz frequency of the antenna slightly reduces without a tumour in the phantom to with a tumour as shown in Figures 8 and 9. This shows that the antenna may have been able to identify the cancer and the alterations in the breast tissue. The tumour tissue in the breast phantom may absorb the radiated radiation due to tumour absorption. It may be possible to estimate the tumour's location in relation to the antenna position by using the major lobe direction. Based on the simulation results, it appears that the antenna can identify whether a tumour is present in the breast phantom. This finding may have significant ramifications for the identification and treatment of breast cancer.

Figure 6: Return loss of antenna without tumour

Figure 7: Return loss with two different tumour sizes

Figure 8: Farfield of the antenna observed without tumour

Figure 9: With tumour farfield result

V. CONCLUSION

The creation of an Ultra-Wideband (UWB) sensor for early BCD serves as a conclusion to this. The main goal was to develop an optimised sensor that could precisely detect breast tumours. The performance of the circular microstrip patch antenna is revealed by the simulation results produced using a breast phantom using CST Studio, both with and without a tumour. An antenna array with precise tumour-related signal detection capabilities. Breast models have undergone extensive testing, optimisation, and simulations, and the results have been impressive in terms of gain of 3.42dBi, directivity of 3, bandwidth of 2.3 GHz to 12.35 GHz centred at 5.4 GHz, and impedance matching. By comparing the data, it was possible to determine that the tumour's existence had an impact on the antenna's performance. A deeper response or a modification of the curve in the S-parameter response points to changes in the antenna impedance matching, scattering behaviour, or interactions with the tumour-affected media. When the tumour was present, the primary lobe in the far-field gain also somewhat decreased. These results imply that the tumour's existence affects the antenna's properties, such as gain, radiation pattern, and impedance matching. Understanding the antenna's performance in breast cancer detection scenarios can be aided by this knowledge. These results also represent the qualities of an effective antenna for medical applications.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This work is partially supported by the UK Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council (EPSRC) under grant EP/X039366/1, and HORIZON-MSCA-RISE ID: 101086492, Marie Skłodowska-Curie, Research and Innovation Staff Exchange (RISE), titled: FractuRe Orthopaedic Rehabilitation: Ubiquitous eHealth Solution (Robust). The authors would also like to acknowledge the technical support from the School of Engineering workshop at Bradford University.

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